

The Impacts of Tribalism and Political Intelligence Towards Ghana and World Development; *21st Century National Assessment of Political and Tribalism Creation effect since Independence on Ghana.*

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ABSTRACT

Attainment of tribal and political objectives has been the main motive and intention of most people in Ghana but is usually done on underground motive basis since independence. Dr Kwame Nkrumah has been tagged as one of the greatest leaders and presidents of Ghana who led Ghana towards independence and freedom. History and all written facts proves this declaration but is now a questionable act and attitude before all as his forward ever, backwards never is not in the right direction and is justified with 21st century downgrade and no proper developments in Ghana. This research and investigation is to establish some real facts in this 21st century on impacts of tribalism and political intelligence towards the development of Ghana since independence. Research findings established that tribal governance and group governance is playing major role in the development and downgrade of projects and activities in Ghana. A good example is the 2012 court ruling and swift four years NDC entry into governance and exit for NPP 8 year's governance which ended in 2024. A strategic move by leaders and knowledgeable men of history and in government when talking about mineral gold production and human gold production in Ghana and worldwide towards world development and governance. Dr Kwame Nkrumah's forward ever backwards never hasn't yielded any positive results for Ghana and Africa implying that the black man is not capable of managing his own affairs. And hence the need to look at the outside world and learn from them when it comes to country development and world development. But if the black man is capable of managing his own affairs, then the human gold products and mineral gold products business should build or generate a beautiful country and world comparable to the Dubai, USA, Britain, Canada etc for the next generations.

Keywords: Tribalism, politics, politicians, impacts, independence, New Democratic Party, New Patriotic Party, governance, gold

INTRODUCTION

The governance and leadership of the Ghanaian economy is full of deceit and lies solely from the world of the sociologist and political scientist. Ghana's attainment of independence in 1957 is a well-established fact based on history but has not yielded any positive results. Graduates in the 21st century are complaining bitterly as the economy is very harsh on them; no jobs, no money, no proper development, acquired loan for projects are left uncompleted or not paid, uncaring attitudes for the common citizen etc. But during political campaigns in election years, are all kinds of promises of job creation, financial breakthroughs, liberation

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unto freedom for all and so forth. But only a few percentage of the national population get the benefit and rewards after election has been done. Based on all happenings in the country and world – wide, it is justified of a world created for the benefit and reward of the sociologist and the political scientist. Not in favor of the scientist, security forces and engineer and if possible the business man. Talk of the presidents, the actors, music industry, the church ministerial level, the minister and all those in governance. All from the political science and sociologist background. For instance, the actor's world is full of fun and enjoyment, all the fame, driving the big cars, the beautiful hotels, living in beautiful buildings, making all the travels (both locally and internationally). Meanwhile, the actor does not write script, just learn the script, act, plays the roles and gets all the fame and enjoyment. Talk of the work of the engineer and scientist involved. How much is his salary or remunerations for creating the beautiful car, nice building, all equipments and gadgets for the movie, radio and TV industry? The sociologist or political scientist is never involved with serious hard work when it comes to creation but the most fortunate in the country or economy when it comes to enjoying the goodies of the land. Talk of the president, minister, the pastor, actor, musician etc, this entire category from the background of the sociologist and political scientist. The Dr Kwame Nkrumah creation and political liberation from political slavery and oppression has never resulted the needed results. If the needed results was ever achieved and attained, then it is on tribal bases as not all have benefited in the Nkrumah generation governance. All happenings, characteristics, features and attributes of most governing bodies since independence is protection of the Nkrumah's tribal freedom liberation. Dr Kwame Nkrumah has been tagged as Fante from Nkroful but that is a true lie and deceit. It is just politically initiated and the only way to siphon and enjoy the goodies and gold resource of Ghana. Have you observed the language tongue of a true Fante? What of the northerner tongue and language? History has it all western migration into the Gold coast was basically around the coast – Fante lands. It could possibly be Akwapim lands as history might tell as Kyerepong and other Akwapim Twi speaking people still exist there comparable to what is found in the Eastern Region of Ghana but in this 21st century as Fante lands. All whites' settlement and governance was around and within the coast. So by generation and creation, Fante's are justified as being British, white tongue users and is justified by the way Fante's speak and the tongues English language speaking smoothness.

What of the tongue of the northerner and people from the northern region, Upper East region and Upper West region. Is there any resemblance of Kwame Nkrumah's tongue with the people from the northern region? Or the same speaking language tongue compared to the tongue of the Fante's. But history has it recorded of Dr Kwame Nkrumah born on 21st September 1909 in Nkroful, Gold Coast. There are written documents to confirm what happened 115 years (1909 -2024) ago. If nothing at all, year of independence 1957 did not have anything like World wide web, internet and digital information sharing system in Ghana for this history to be justified before all. The Ghanaian gold has been locked into an account and I believe it's an account led by the Dr Kwame Nkrumah total liberation and fight for

freedom. If Dr Kwame Nkrumah fought for freedom and liberation and won, did he win all the gold inclusive? In which account did he leave the gold production business in Ghana. Does Kwame Nkrumah marriage with the Fathia Ritzk, an Egyptian Coptic bank worker and former teacher ring a bell? Lived in exile in Conakry, Guinea as the guest of President Ahmed Sekou Toure, who made him honorary co – president of the country? These are all penned down raw facts but what is happening in the 21st century Ghana. Talk of all the 16 regions in Ghana. In terms of regions to tribe's ratio, northerners ration to other regions is 3:13. Look at current migration issues in Ghana and the rate of country deteriorating attitude. Does the 2024 political election year ring any bell? What of the chosen presidential candidate for the NPP and NDC?

Why this take off after a total world shutdown (during the Akuffo Addo Dankwa led government) and a new take off of the world in 2019/2020 Covid. Never expect a pilot/driver to pilot/drive through storms and take over the piloting/driver wheels in safe mode or periods. This is comparably like a new creation for the next generation and a complete automatic and force take off by the northerner creation. Can't this be comparable to Nkrumah take off in 1957 after obtaining freedom from the British? How many northerners tongue speakers and users compared to southern tongue/British tongue users and speakers among the BIG SIX who fought for independence? You and I were not there but possibly the 60 years old political scientist or sociologist was at the polling station and therefore can attest or justify that fact. These are questions worth investigating and analyzing for the good will of Ghanaians, the British and the world at large. This is simply because of the downward direction of the country full of lies, corruption, fifth and supposed governance and development of country through loans/grants from donor partners and so forth.

Who can depend solely on loan from a bank, financial institution or friend without a repayment plan when talking about greatness in life or development of a country? Can one get continues loan from a bank without repayment plan before another loan? Assuming Mr A going for a loan for about 10 times from Ghana Commercial Bank (GCB) worth GHC20,000 amounting to Ghc200,000 without repayment plan. Is it not for the GCB to go bankrupt? There will be a total crush of GCB if this is extended to 1000 population who needs loans with this same motive. Then what of receiving loans from China continuously for instance for all projects in Ghana without a repayment plan. Won't China go bankrupt or run the country's money down. Is the white man ever in a position to do this, give money continuously to a country for development without a repayment plan? Is China willing to do this for all other countries? Why won't the country Ghana be full of uncompleted projects? Most of these uncompleted projects have being in that manner for a purpose. All these because of the issue of money. What the Ghanaian will say '*sika asem*'. *Who doesn't need money? Developed countries are developing at a faster rate because of money. Who doesn't want to be rich, who doesn't love better things. We all love goodies and need development as a country Ghana and people. What a Nigerian will call a money ritual, a Ghanaian will call money medicine – sika aduro, to heal poverty or money sickness. Hence it is justifiable for Ghanaian to sort or look*

for a new way of solving Ghanaian problems rather than building a country solely dependent on loans or grants from foreign partners. The issue of building Ghanaian economy based on loans and grants is another questionable act with several big international mineral gold mining companies dotted around the country. Ghana as a country is full of gold mines generating billions of pounds sterling's and cedis and various real mineral and human gold bars on monthly basis. There exist a missing link or question mark somewhere pointing in the direction of tribalism and political lies in Ghana political setup worth researching and justifying.

Can you think of the rate at which people from other African countries are entering Ghana through Burkina Faso, Togo, Nigeria and making Ghana ugly and filthy all in the names of collection of scrapes? They just pick some wrist watches, nail cutters, dresses, mats, bags etc walks all the way from other African countries and Burkina Faso and into Ghana. This are all northerner tribal related. Looks like other African countries do not want the peace and greatness of Ghana and the Ghanaian economy. This has made the Ghanaian environment and economy too ugly. It has even increased the rate of illegal gold mining business in Ghana destroying forest reserves, lands and water bodies. At Nsutam in the Eastern Region of Ghana for instance is the total destruction of river Birim and Supong. These are things worth investigating and analyzing by security professionals for the good will and wellbeing of mother Ghana.

These are various questions worth justifying through this research to see the main motive of the tribal and political intelligence in Ghana towards development since independence to the 21st century. Then what possible deductions can be made for readjustment and refinement towards the development of Ghana for the next generation.

2 JUSTIFICATION OF RAW FACTS ON POLITICAL LIES

2.1 Wearing of Fugu (Northerner Cloth) during independence Speech before Ghanaians and the World.

Justification for actions and inactions are evidenced based and a good example is the celebration of Independence Day after a great battle by the Nkrumah led government against our colonial masters which is the British. Based on raw facts, documentaries and other printable documents, the day of independence against the British by the government led movement towards independence was celebrated with a speech but one symbolic item is the '**dress code**' of the big six. They were all in Fugu attire of which a speech was shared. All Ghanaian tribes in Ghana celebrates symbols of unity, citizenship, tribal traits, a sense of belonging through language and mother tongue, food, clothing, facial appearances etc. One can easily identify the tribe of a fellow Ghanaian through the cloth he/she wears or way of dressing. And Fugu in Ghana is always associated with people of the three northern regions especially in the case of Ghana. And if possible in other African countries. So wearing Fugu on the day of independence to celebrate the victory after a hard battle is something related to

the northerner. Or in simple terms, it justifies a victory for Ghana or Gold Coast against the British led by the Northerner. This declarations can be analyzed in various ways through logical reasoning and its implications;

- It's a complete northerners registration in battle for victory and independence
- A battle for Ghana or Gold Coast led by Dr Kwame Nkrumah who is a northerner
- A political party and winning government belonging to the northerner
- Takeover government from the British led by the northern
- A moslem movement to rule and govern the Gold Coast or Ghana led by the northerner (about 80% Moslems in Ghana) and the world
- A change in government and religion from Christian religion to Islamic religion
- A well created world and government in the direction of greatness and development changed and reversed in the direction of retraction (Negative way of the statement Forward ever Backward never); this is a fact based on 21st century development in Ghana.
- Motive of taking over Gold Coast or Ghana from a well created and intelligent man from an African country based on gold in Ghana. When one looks at movement and shipment of Gold and money from Ghana towards other African countries and final verdict of ending in some African countries and exit from the earth. This is detailed below.

Again, Nkrumah is tagged as someone from the Western Region of Ghana. This can be true and a complete lie to the common Ghana. This is because no one can confidently tell or give correct facts concerning the administrative regions in Ghana during the Gold Coast day's era. A good example is 10 regions in Ghana comparable to the current 16 regions which is a complete change in terms of new names, geographical position system (GPS) and position of town, community, city or future city. But based on language tongue and dress code, it's a complete lie to tell or explain to someone that president Dr Kwame Nkrumah is a Fante or from the Western Region of Ghana. It is a complete lie which is worth further analyzing based on Fante's ways of life, Nkrumah's declaration and support for Forward Ever Backwards Never couple with current state and affairs of development in Ghana.

Look at it this way again. No human life or being can tell where he/she comes from except by a mother, father, elderly family members or someone. And this citizenship is from the town or community or city where your head with eyes entered into the world. Citizenship coming from where one's eyes opened to see the new world or creation. That is citizenship being established from the basis of where one is born into the world. This is the reason for citizenship by birth but even that is a question mark? Where final justification is also

associated with motive, attitude, actions and contribution towards national and world development. If a real citizen of a town or community is terrorizing and fighting against the system or community, he/she can be thrown off board or into prisons. So if Dr Kwame Nkrumah's forward ever backwards never is justified with this 21st century Ghana downgrade when dealing and talking about country development and greatness, then there is a missing link worth looking for and fixing. Or there is complete political lies to the advantage of someone somewhere.

2.2 Shipment of Gold and Money to Guinea and landing in Guinea

Dr Kwame Nkrumah is tagged the best ever president Ghana had ever registered in the world while others think if he hadn't embarked on his change in rulership and governance from the British, Ghana would have been a better country. Ghana's way of life, greatness and development would have been comparably the same like other western world countries. Because I believe the whole wide world was set on one platform and asked to move in the direction of greatness and development after the Second World War. This is simple because, one can easily see the creation of a beautiful world of development and greatness in terms of science and engineering in most African Countries. This well created and generated world is the same in the western World. Such beautiful engineered world is seen in most cities of African countries and same in the western world. A good example is Ghana, Senegal, Gambia, Burkina Faso, Nigeria etc. Travel to Accra, Dakar, Banjul and carefully look at the city settings, drainage works, the tall and massive state institutions buildings and they are comparably same as in the western world. This creation should have been taking on a modelling approach, education and training through university intelligence and simulated throughout the country for a western land and city world generation. So it means a world was created out of technology and intelligence for the world to revolve around education, training, planting and generating of such world continuously. A reason for most western countries having the same life in terms of intelligence and development.

But looks like a cycle was broken in terms of a world towards greatness and beauty on the African continent by the Nkrumah led movement. By all assessment and investigations, it looks like that creation was a Christian religion related creation and hence towards salvation, beauty, the goodwill of mankind and great height attainment for the common citizen. But the Nkrumah led movement which I think is Islamic religion focused broke that creation and development cycle. But lied to the common citizen with the phrase 'Forward ever Backwards Never'. The true reflection and work done by his statement is the current state of Ghana. This is an investigation from one school of thought where one school of thought may prove or want to prove otherwise.

What of the possibility of the Nkrumah led government and world leaders creating and generating a world of greatness and beauty for the world but from the African continent or soil? Where a gold production business and intelligence is generated from Africa to create all

kinds of beautiful places and world and hence the need to send the common African into slavery to serve in different fields or capacity through good leadership of a white man and hence a resultant impact or effect on the African Continent. Where at any point in time, a beautiful country or world is created and set as center stage focal point for greatness in all dimensions. A good example is China, other Asian countries and Dubai for instance. Have you ever thought about the world of Football competition between African countries in the 1990's and in 2025 today? Can Ghana or Nigeria Football team face Chinese team, Korean team and possibly Saudi Arabia national team in this 21st Century? These are all thoughts worth analyzing and further probing. It's possibly it was human gold and mineral gold production intelligent creation to help the world as a world where you and I may be part of a world and not part of the world when it comes to enjoying or assessing the goodies of the land or soil. But from the objective and perspective of United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN - SDG's), resources are supposed to be shared equitably in life to the advantage of all.

2.3 Bombing at Burkina Faso during Nkrumah Visit

From the world of investigation and research, can it be a possibility that Ghana is being ruled by Burkina Faso, Ivory Coast and Togolese. That is being governed by three French speaking countries? Where there is intelligent creation motive but the ability to unravel the secrets and mysteries in there is very difficult? Is it also possible that Ghana is being used by this same Burkina Faso, Ivory Coast, Togolese and other African countries to propagate an agenda of mineral and human gold production to the detriment of the common Ghanaian or one who have lived in Ghana for several years? These are well researched investigations with some raw facts but worth further probing and investigating. Think of the northerner, Ivory Coast and Togolese populations and numbers in Ghana in this 21st Century. And comparably think and investigate the rate of migration from Burkina Faso, Ivory Coast and Togo which are all Francophone countries. Is there any correlation between Gold Coast and Ivory Coast? An Anglophone country and Francophone country? A British colony country and French colony country? Is there a relationship between the one who owns and mines the gold called gold trade because the country is involved in gold mining production? And the one involved in ivory trade which is basically buying and selling of ivory (tusks of elephants). Is there any explanation between a French speaking personality comparable to the attributes and features of an English speaking personality? Think of the number of Ghanaian communities and towns in the three countries named or registered above. So assuming a gold production business is set up; both human gold and mineral gold with the current rate of migration from Burkina Faso, Ivory Coast and Togo, who benefits? Who benefits from a well-crafted gold mining business establishment and takeover by these three neighbouring countries in Ghana with their huge numbers and representation in terms of population and manipulation? Assuming Dr Kwame Nkrumah is from Burkina and decides with Ivory Coast, Togo and other Francophone African countries leaders to set up such a business through Ghana, who benefits? Can you imagine how some graduates in Ghana do not get jobs or gets employed in

gold mines and state institutions after tertiary educations? These are all questionable acts and behaviours of some secrets, actions and inactions in Ghana when talking about 21st century development in Ghana, mineral gold and human gold production worldwide. Assuming this was a creation from Burkina Faso or cooperation and collaboration between the two or more countries and bombing at Burkina Faso for execution of the next intelligence creation direction as discussed by some schools of thoughts or at Kulungugu by another school of thought.

2.4 Forward Ever, Backwards Never

The main objective statement which is the center stage of Dr Kwame Nkrumah's led leadership and government is 'Forward Ever Backwards Never'. But a big question we all Ghanaians and a world ought to ask is the meaning, the intelligence and motive in this statement and hence the struggle and battle for freedom and liberation from the governance and rulership of the British. Some are of the assertions that if the British had ruled Ghana and no need for change or the Nkrumah's fight, Ghana would have been better off. It would have been competition in the direction of greatness in terms of beauty and development among other countries. Can you look at the current state of development in Ghana in terms of everything? And the current destruction if possible all resources coupled with corruption among leaders and the youth. Then again, the generation of a country who thinks and believes complete allegiance to God in terms of song and prayer builds a beautiful country. Everybody in Ghana wants to travel not thinking and knowing that Ghana is someone's or another countries abroad. Therefore the need to think and create an abroad or country of international status comparable to other countries to attract tourist and develop. Then build a country that will train good scientist and engineers to grow and propagate the country to the next level. Just like we have Ghanaians and other countries nationals in USA working and paying allegiance towards the goodwill and welfare of the USA, other people are in Ghana doing same for their own welfare and countries or nations of origin greatness. And hence Ghanaians needs to think alike or in the same direction. It is possible the Dr Nkrumah's leadership and government generated a world in the direction of current Dubai to revolve round the world towards greatness and development and hence Forward Ever, backwards Never. Therefore, it's the time of Ghanaians to learn, think, create and generate a world in that direction. This is after serious work for Ghanaians and the world. OR it could mean Dr Nkrumah embarked on a selfish and greedy ambition for the welfare of other countries or a world to the detriment of the common Ghanaian. Simply because he wasn't from Ghana and do not wants the welfare and greatness of Ghana but need the gold for his people. Therefore the intelligent creation of a gold mining business for his welfare and good people. A justification for telling Ghanaians I, Dr Kwame Nkrumah will go forward it terms of countries greatness and development. Whiles backwards in terms of countries enrichment is for Ghanaian's Presidents and his people. Therefore a justification for Forward Ever, Backwards Never. Can you think of the current management of all state resources and items coupled with unwillingness to serve one another? The level of corruption and non-allegiance of security forces to government and non-adherence to rules and laws

governing a community or country by citizens? All these negative impacts or effects have proven the negative way of forward ever, backwards never! When this is compared to the governance, operation and management of state resources by the white man and in the western world even though to a certain level (not at level of a probability of 1). So we Ghanaians ought to think and probe further into Dr. Kwame's Nkrumah's creation and ask serious questions worth researching for answers, the meaning and motive of 'Forward Ever Backwards Never'. Based on the current state and affairs in Ghana where a degree holder graduates from school, completes mandatory work to country and state then sits home for years looking for job.

2.5 Free Senior High School Government Policy and Political Intelligence

From the first point above, logical reasoning and its implications, this is rightly applicable to FREE SHS education in Ghana led by the Nana Addo Dankwa Akuffo Addo government. Was FREE SHS Akuffo Addo's main objective or objective by the former Vice President, Alhaji Mahamudu Bawumai as the second in command but a captain and president for another world or tribe propagating political agenda in an intelligent manner? Who enjoys free education in Ghana most? And in which regions are all the Aids and free money given and generating geared towards in Ghana. I for instance have never enjoyed free education in Ghana and most people in the southern sector are in the same position. Can you imagine the number of scholarships that was given to tertiary students during the 2016 – 2024 Akuffo Dankwa led government gave to Ghanaians tertiary students in Ghana? The total sum of money used to spearhead this scholarships can even build three or four international gold mines in Ghana to help build the Ghanaian economy. I am not against given scholarships but ask of the quality human gold products that are being produced towards national and world development. Then all these actions against stealing and syphoning of government money by Headmasters, Administrators, directors, ministers where raw facts proves of a headmaster buying two cars to the detriment of teachers and staff. Avoiding the opportunity of using this money to complete an administration block for a school. And right after the exit of the Akuffo Addo's led government out of office and into election is the Nkrumah's wining and victory attitude; Mr Mahama on the right for election and Dr Bawumai on the left for election towards a total or complete northerner led government registration and take off as pilot after a new world creation – COVID 19 period. Is there a possibility for another project or simulation for another Mr Mahama on the right for election and Dr Bawumai on the left for election towards a total or complete northerner led government registration and take off as pilot in the future with current rambling and tangling in NPP presidential elections? These are questionable acts and raw facts before all Ghanaians and world worth looking into with a deeper and microscopic piecing microscope.

Based on research, investigations from studies areas and Nsutam with illegal gold mining intelligence and motive, I think there is a tribe called Asanteman. Which in terms of phonetics basically looks or literally means; '*yE san ate oman*' - *Asanteman*. This in English means

'Establishing another nation or kingdom' again. This is where one sits down lazily, folds the arms, thinks he/she is smart and intelligent and ask one or the worker to do all the donkey or difficult works with a final take over with guns and intelligence as a thief. Which is one school of thought based on divine creation and Bible and young guys of today's intelligence and nonsensical insults to business owners and job creators. Think of the current Asanteman explanation and registration at Nsutam in the Eastern Region of Ghana. Where people living in some philosophical world, school of thoughts or regions just gets small scale gold mining certificates from other regions and ends up in Eastern Region for contracts. The contracts are awarded by Newmont Akyem at Abirim with final output for work done to be the destruction of land, water resources, forest reserves, farmlands etc all in the name and philosophy of illegal gold mining. Newmont is where all the nice creation and creative works dealing with gold mining and production are done and completed. Such small scale miners are involved or works in another destruction creators hands justified by the destruction of natural resources and properties worth Billions of Pounds Sterling's, dollars and cedis with even loss of human lives. This is the case of the COVID – 19 worldwide which is possibly a problem or solution from one philosophical world or school of thought.

3 21ST CENTURY ASSESSMENT OF GHANA

3.1 21st Century Development in Ghana

The 21st century generation, citizens and population in Ghana are bitter and angry at the current state of affairs when talking about job creation, greatness and development of a country. It is on most or all mindset of citizens of Ghana that to make it in life or reach the self-actualization level on the Maslow's hierarchy of needs, one ought to travel. Citizens do not have faith in the economy, one does not see opportunity when it comes to job creation and accessibility. Even though opportunity comes in different forms, everyone and his knowledge level and hence resultant perception in life. As to whether the opportunity is small or big. I think leaders in Ghana wants graduates and the unemployed to make use of their intelligence and mental capacity towards helping themselves, building the economy and meeting their needs as represented in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG's). But I think everyone and his mental development process and hence the attainment of a great intelligence and its application at a stage or point in life. It therefore deems fit for leaders to help the vulnerable in the society or country, educate, train and give jobs as a government. This will help them meet the basic physiological needs in life, help themselves and families. Then think through how to better their lives while working assiduously to climb the Maslow's' hierarchy of needs ladder in life and help develop the country.

The rate of development in Ghana isn't in the right direction as stated by Dr Kwame Nkrumah in his statement of forward ever, backwards never. All developments in Ghana are highly political and party initiated and implemented. An uncompleted project by party A has a lower probability that it will be completed by party B. Fanteakwa South district and Eastern Region

of Ghana for instance has a lot of uncompleted projects undergoing deteriorating process and extinction from the earth. This motive by government in power leads to wastage in terms of resources, unemployment and financial burden on all at the end of every government tenure. A justification for wastage of graduate's intelligence and ability, four years wastage in the university in Ghana and other African countries. This is a problem worth investigating and analyzing when it comes to development on participatory approach and not on the basis of party tickets or party lines. Ghana needs development on all fronts; roads constructions, buildings or housing facilities, drainage networks, sewage networks, bioengineering works, hospitals construction, in the education sectors, water resources management, treatments and distribution, afforestation, job creation etc. It's a basic principle to learn from others and that ought to be the motive of the young generation when it comes to the development and management of the economy. Everyone is a government as anyone can be a president today from the concept of school off thought. The very way one wants to be an assembly man, another member of parliament (MP) and another a Minister towards the presidency as president. The next 50 years president is being admitted at Kindergarten or Primary one (1) today which is a scenario but a reality too. Everyone knows something to the extent of even a mad man knowing something for going through madness school of thought which you, a so called healthy individual has never attended or graduated from before. Therefore, if your mental capacity has developed to the extent of being a leader, never use it to intimidate or bully others. In a nutshell, act responsibly when the duty of responsibility lies on your shoulders. Everyone and his mental capacity development stage in life. Ghana needs to look at the development and country building intelligence by other countries and work on going in that same direction.

3.2 21st Century Management and State institutions Collaboration and partnership in state affairs.

Management of state institution by current generation is very bad with high degree of quest for money first and not offering services for giveaways by clients or customers. Most state institution are in a very bad state and people or managers are not willing to share views, accepts corrections or implement recommendations. Most private and some institutions are not managed in that manner. Money oriented managers and directors operating as group have made the state institutions their own property and not willing to allow the system flow for good controlling and operation by able hands. The state of collaboration that is supposed to exist between state institutions and generate money into government accounts or coffers for projects and initiatives is very poor. This is draining government pocket and accounts on monthly basis as payments for government workers is on monthly basis. Most countries progress and development is basically based on generating of income and money by all state institutions in a collaborative manner. But this is not same in Ghana as most institutions are operated loosely and generating money into individual's hands and pockets. For instance;

- Payment for tariffs (water, electricity) to Ghana Water Company, Water Resources Commission and Electricity Company of Ghana for water and power (electricity) usage. Effective management of accrued money for services offered for all water projects, usage in the water industry and in the power industry.
- Payment of road user fee at Tollbooth to Ghana Highway Authority for roads constructions and management of roads.
- Generation of revenue through police reports, arrests, illegalities by Ghana Police Services and Security Forces
- Fees paying and profits generations from the Ghana Education Service instead of free education (FREE SHS).
- Treatment of all illness and disease at a cost by Ghana Health Service professionals to generate funds into government accounts etc.
- Revenue generations from the Registrar's Generals Department through business registrations, certifications, monitoring and quarterly or yearly returns analysis.
- Revenues (tax) generation from all state and public bodies and individuals by Ghana Revenue Authority and its Collectors for government projects planting and establishments etc.
- Researches and investigations by security forces like immigration services, Ghana Navy, Ghana Military and gives results like from Natural Resources Conservation Services in hydrology and hydraulics. Results and outputs generated from such institutions becomes data that can be sold and money generated into government coffers or is used by the state institutions. For instance, climate data and rainfall data from Meteorological services Department etc.

From the above assertions, it's well justified that state institutions are supposed to work by coordinating and collaborating with each other. Then generate money through partnership and collaboratively for the running of the institution and into government accounts for picking and planting jobs for the unemployed graduates in Ghana and worldwide.

3.3 The 21st Century Forward Ever, Backwards Never Ghana

If another Ghana is to be built to justify the positive side and direction of forward ever backwards never comparable to Ghana in 2025 as said by Dr Kwame Nkrumah! Then the leaders and sitting government need to work collaboratively and not on tribal basis or on tribal grounds. It looks like Ghana is deteriorating simply because of the concept of ownership and leadership in Ghana. Every tribe wants to prove to be the owners of the land and hence comparably the same motive in the minds of leaders of the country in every regard. But Ghana needs to develop and generate a beautiful wealthy country through participatory approach

and collaboration. In this way the following recommendations and points can be analyzed or probed, reviewed further and applied if applicable;

- Build a beautiful modern city like a university, estate or institution with all facilities with modern intelligence and engineering eg is University of Environment and Sustainable Development under construction at Bunso in the Eastern Region of Ghana. A possible change in university name but with same building concept and intelligence as a model for the new Ghana.
- The modern intelligence and engineering will includes, good tall buildings, good housing buildings and facilities, good roads, good electrification system, beautiful drainage networks, proper sewage systems, beautiful bioengineering works, well-constructed and coordinated state institutions, good management and collaborative way of making money into government accounts by all state institutions, creating a system where the education system purposely trains children and the young to take over and operate such a project or country development.
- The above deliberation will constitute the accoutrements or components of a whole one catchment area even though there might be small catchments within this catchment.
- This catchment will be comparable to one complete zone within a town or city with meeting roads around it.
- Then building a complete town or city made up of several catchments will be by picking the architectural design and mounting it catchment by catchment with little or some modifications. This is simply because engineering deals with real time simulation based on feasibility studies of geographical location, associated characteristics of project area, seasons of siting of project and other factors.
- Then simulation of the project over the whole town, city, region and country.
- There will be the building of big malls, entertainment places with some monuments and edifices of beauty for entertainments and happy moods generations during holidays and weekends.
- The whole water resources sector will be worked on regionally by engineers towards generating a pure quality clean water to meet the SDG's. Then obtain water flowing under high pressures for hydropower projects and those with large surface areas that can allow boats and ships to move one as learning and entertainment sources.
- There will be waste management sector to manage all wastages and generated wastes in the country towards obtaining a clean towns, cities and country comparable to some western countries like UK, USA, and Dubai, Germany etc. Since waste management and usage is problem, one can employ lecturers in the waste management sector to

hold the process together. This intelligence will be applied to cover various sectors of the economy as a clean and beautiful city and country is generated for the now and future generations.

- Generation of such a project will be through collaborative approach and engineered. A whole catchment project will constitute a team led by an experienced engineer supervisor. And working under the engineer supervisor will be all kinds of workers or experts that can handle a whole estate building project. ***A good example is the modelled University of Environment and Sustainable Development project at Bunso in the Eastern Region of Ghana.*** Such a project is a big employment industry for the unemployed graduate and all. And with this, migrating to abroad will be on lesser note or with a different motive.
- Such a project will generate a beautiful country for Ghana and with a possibility of simulating for the whole world. Simulating for the whole wide world is regardless. It simply means taking it to the ends of the world where it doesn't exist.

3.4 World Development and impacts from Real time Political Intelligence

3.4.1 Establishment of Ministry of Goldway Worldwide

Money is the first and foremost important parameter and symbol which quantifies anything on planet earth whenever one is talking about buying and selling worldwide. Money is a gold which means a real precious mineral (or figure) when dealing with buying and selling in terms of exchange of goods and services. Everyone on planet earth talks and deals with money basically meaning we are all involved with money issues or problems one way or the other. The government talks about money, the government worker talks and deals with money, the estate developer deals with money, the scientist, the engineer, the pilot, the mechanic, the trader or seller at the market, the banker and the common citizen in the society. So in summary, everyone deals and talks about money with the only difference being the particular currency at any point in time. That is either the pounds sterling's, the dollar, Euro, the cedis, CFA, yen, Naira. These are all money with different symbols of authority based on country, history, allegiance, geographical locations, features, determining factors and finally a weighting factor highly dependent on countries development and impact on the world and its development. And this currency or money is what is moving and developing a country based on inflows and outflows into individual hands, business, home, job or business. But in all these assertions, there is one important group or categories who are dealing with money at any time 't' when talking about buying and selling in real life. And that is the trader or the market man/woman. The beans seller, the meat seller, that rice and flour supplier and any other person at the market. The cashier at the bank or banker deals with money but not in terms of direct selling and buying of goods. Why am I interested in the trader or seller at the market when it comes to money, national development and world development in Ghana? Most countries have all kinds of institutions playing different roles and these institutions have been

classified as one body contributing to the welfare and development of oneself, country and world. For instance is the Ministry of Education, Ministry of Défense, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Water Resources, Ministry of Health, Ministry of Gender, Ministry of Roads and Highways, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Communication, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Ministry of Sports, Ministry of Energy etc. Most of these ministries are common among countries worldwide with some being different from the other. But possibly with the same roles and responsibilities in a country's management or world development. This is a clear indication of landing spot that is either as a world controller or country control room operator. So basically this is a reason for some ministries having the same name, the same representation and responsibility in all countries worldwide. The same with different names and less representation worldwide. In totality, it means it's possible some don't know how a ministry in government is formed or established while others may have been on that difficult road which leads to a beautiful destination in real life before.

In Ghana for instance which is the research area and main country of focus for data, analysis and scenario generations, there are all kinds of classifications forming a ministry in Government. Examples includes the above listed ministries worldwide which gives thousands of jobs and wages and salaries to employees on monthly basis with associated taxes . These taxes ends up in government account or coffers for various activities towards job creation and world development. But ask yourself if the market woman selling eggs, beans, distributing rice and flour, the factory worker, the graphic designer, the wakye seller in that corner of the street is **effectively taxed** on monthly basis and contributing to country and world development? The Ghana Revenue Authority (GRA) and revenue collectors have been given this responsibility, but how effective is the collection and taxing system? Compare this to a medical Doctor Husband and accountant wife forming a family who are taxed before payment at the end of the month or salary or wages hitting the personal bank account. Think of this scenario for instance, taxing two families where family A is working for the government and family B are traders not paying taxes or being taxed effectively at the end of the month. All the analyzed figures are applicable in all currencies worldwide.

Table 1: Two family taxing system analysis (Gh¢ or ¢)

	Family A		Family B	
	Husband (Doctor)	Wife (Accountant)	Husband (Mechanic)	Wife (Rice Distributor)
Monthly Salary	Gh¢10,000	Gh¢8,000	Gh¢7,500	Gh¢6,000
Monthly Tax (10%)	Gh¢1000	Gh¢800	Gh¢750	Gh¢600
Yearly Tax	Gh¢12,000	Gh¢9,600	Gh¢9,000	Gh¢7,200
Total Contribution by Family per Year	Gh¢108,000		Gh¢16,200	
Ten Years Contribution Effect	Gh¢1,080,000		Gh¢162,000	

Research findings establishes the salary or wages for husband Doctor and wife accountant payable by the government on monthly basis. But then, there is a procedure which justifies the ¢10,000 for husband and ¢8,000 for wife monthly wages based on work input on daily

basis. Let assume the husband mechanic saves ₵250 on daily basis for 30days average for all months in a year. Then also into daily savings of ₵200 for 30 days average for the wife for the whole year round. Then for a monthly salary for the husband mechanic is ₵7,500 and ₵6000 for the Rice distributor and the corresponding taxing analysis above. This is on a lower scale or level. But what of on a higher scale or level as in the case of distributing point shops or factory where a seller a trader picks good and pays ₵2000 upfront? In such a situation, a business owner or trader can pay or save ₵5000 per day. This is analyzed in the **Table 2** below comparable to a government earner in that category.

Table 2: Two family taxing system analysis on a higher level (Gh¢ or ¢)

	Family A		Family B	
	Husband (Director)	Wife (Accountant)	Husband (Car Dealer)	Wife (Goods Distributor)
Monthly Salary	Gh¢60,000	Gh¢40,000	Gh¢1,000,000	Gh¢1,500,000
Monthly Tax (10%)	Gh¢6,000	Gh¢4,000	Gh¢100,000	Gh¢150,000
Yearly Tax	Gh¢72,000	Gh¢48,000	Gh¢1,200,000	Gh¢1,800,000
Total Contribution by Family per Year	Gh¢120,000		Gh¢3,000,000	
Ten Years Contribution Effect	Gh¢1,200,000		Gh¢30,000,000	

Analysis from **Table 1** and **Table 2** gives a clear indication that the government of Ghana is losing huge sums of money on monthly, yearly and decade basis for the trader or seller who is not taxed. And it is possibly same in countries or regions where the tax collecting system in that country is not well regulated in the market sector or in the buying and selling business sector. Think of the two families having three wards each who graduates in the university in years to come with undergraduate degrees to doctor of philosophy level and to be employed by the government of Ghana or the government. One can ask himself or herself. What is the contribution by the two families towards tax generation or income for the government, job creation in the country, national development and world development? These and many more reasons for the **MINISTRY OF GOLWAY** establishment in Ghana, other countries and if possible worldwide. This is where all traders will be classified under one body or institution (**MINISTRY OF GODWAY**) and under it is a business entity or company called **GLORY SUSU** and other departments. This will be a company or business entity that will be employed to generate monthly income for all traders, sellers, drivers, fashion designers, and other professionals not classified under one umbrella in government. It will be simply generating a monthly salary, wages or income around whatever business one is running, spearheading or involved in. But it is subject to all kinds of conditions with the poor trader in mind because of sustainability of business, family he or she is running, daily earnings and the inflows and outflows of money in business. And out of the generated monthly salary for the trader will be a percentage for income tax for government comparable to the percentage income tax from government workers in Ghana and worldwide into government account on monthly basis. The percentage for tax will depend on all kinds of factors used to generate income tax for the worker in government and will be the same for the government worker. In Ghana for instance is 16.6%

as according to my payslip. This **MINISTRY OF GOLDWAY** is applicable to all countries worldwide who have difficulty when it comes to the collection and accountability for income tax from the trader or seller in the market. The currency (Gh¢) used here (**Table 1 & 2**) as a scenario is also applicable to all currencies worldwide like the dollar (\$), pound sterling's (£), CFA France, Euro (€) etc.

3.4.2 Establishment of Ministry of Management and Maintenance Worldwide

Management and maintenance issue especially in the case of state owned institutions facilities and buildings is a major problem in Ghana and possibly same in other countries worldwide. With this under discussion, it is of utmost importance in this 21st century to have a body or institution that works in that direction as all and everybody on earth is now concern with beauty and aesthetics at all levels. It is necessary to have a body that will give or generate a structure or system that will keep these institutions anew and fresh always. Assuming Ghana decides to build modern towns, cities and country to international standards with everything in place. How do we keep the beauty, aesthetics and freshness always? There is therefore the need for another ministry that will basically look at how or ensures the renovation of state institutions, roads, sewage system, government projects, private projects etc through self-financing intelligence (by the ministry itself) and money generation process towards beauty of the system, country and for sustainability. There is therefore the need for the establishment of **MINISTRY OF MANAGEMENT AND MAINTENANCE** to cater for all management and how to maintain the well-built or generated town, city or country always anew all year round. By this declaration, I mean there will be a fund generation process to cater for the paintings, bioengineering works and little addition or modifications of all state institutions, housing systems, private structures, projects and other areas deemed fit and appropriate. Think of this simple simulation to generate money internally for this ministry on monthly basis and major maintenances works done within 6 months or on yearly basis. The scenario is applicable in all other currencies worldwide and highly dependent on population. Populations living in housing system is by estimation and hence subject to real time research and investigations in every country. But there is a high degree of confidence in estimating population size in this research work as detailed in **Table 3**.

Determining factors upon which population size in housing system depends includes;

- Development status of country
- Size of economy, job creation and accessibility potential
- Migrations
- Education levels
- Languages
- Housing system and accessibility etc.

And upon critical consideration and examination of these factors carefully, the percentage population that are living in housing system and will be able to pay Gh¢20 ranges from 50% - 60%. This is the case for Ghana but is applicable to all population countries worldwide at possibly the same rate but different currency interpretations.

Table 3: Monthly and Yearly estimation of Total amount generated to feed the Ministry of Management and Maintenance in its operation

Country	Amount Per head/ Family Size (Per Month)	Total Population Per Each Country	Population in Housing System (Per Estimate)	Total Amount per Month	Total Amount per Year
Ghana	Gh¢20	34.43Million	18Million	Gh¢360Million	Gh¢43.2Billion
UK	£20	68.2Million	34Million	£680Million	£8.16Billion
United States of America	\$20	339.8Million	200Million	\$4Billion	\$48Billion

3.4.3 Establishment of Ministry of Lotteries and Bettings

The lotteries institution or organization has been in existence over several decades with the inception of the technological betting industry (sporting industry for instance). With modern intelligence and interest in the sporting industry, the lotteries industry and betting industry is a big sector worth considering and taking to the next level in government. Especially in the case of analyzing the quantum of money generated on daily, weekly, monthly and yearly basis from the lotteries and betting industry. With new creation intelligence, formation and its associated establishment of new ministries in government, it deems fit to add more ministries which have an impact parameter or factor. The Lotteries and betting industry has huge quantum of money in its coffers or accounts comparable to other newly formed ministries in Government in Ghana for instance. This is especially in the case of Ghana's government like the ministry of Tourism, Ministry of Fisheries and aquaculture (This is same Ministry of Agriculture), Ministry of Communication (same as Ministry of Information). The above-mentioned ministries have been worked on and classified already with Ministry of Tourism for instance in Ghana money generation for ministry operations and impact on Ghana's economy and development on a minimal level. But think and ask of the impacts of the Lotteries and Betting industry in Ghana in terms of wealth generation, country and world development, keeping faith and hope alive in the life's of the unemployed graduate, the common citizen, the monthly income level of lottery and betting lovers, tax into government coffers, projects, the happy mode generation philosophy around the lottery, betting and sporting games in Ghana and worldwide and finally the employment industry created or generated? It's worth to be classified to another level in Ghana and given international recognition in government. These

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are few reasons for the need for the establishment of **MINISTRY OF LOTTERIES AND BETTINGS** in Ghana and worldwide. Under the ministry will be the National Lottery Authority (NLA) which is operational in Ghana, the National Betting Authority (NBA) and other departments under them playing pivotal roles. Then at the University level will be the **School of Lotteries and Bettings** as a school of thought worth teaching and learning, understanding by students for country and world development. Because the lottery Sheet/book in Ghana for instance is a big mathematics manual worth understanding and analyzing. It comprises subjects or topics like permutation (*perm*) as used by lotto lovers, combinations, additions, subtractions, factorials, week endings (used by teachers for lesson plans preparations), dates in the month, dates or years of events etc. This is a whole school of thought whose manual is released on weekly basis (Mondays for the week) in Ghana for study and getting the five lotto numbers (as answers) after vigorous study and analysis then stamping final authority on it with money for a price or fee or winning amount according to marking scheme, which is the five numbers to be released by the lotto machines. This is the old lotto system in Ghana with results released on Saturdays at 5pm according to research and findings. The concept of Bettings also comprises of additions, subtractions, logical reasoning, graphs analysis, odds determinations, fractions, weigh factors determination, teams' history, achievement levels, computer programming's and a whole mathematical concept and philosophies. And these are all university courses and various schools of thoughts worth investigations and researching into. It's again a good way of learning everything about a sporting game or activity (Football, Basketball, Volleyball, Rugby, Cricket etc) and keeping the data or records for history and unborn generations.

Someone might ask as to whether Lottery and Bettings is worth but according to the biblical books, *'Jesus cloth was used for this same purpose towards proving a school of thought or investigating something after being hanged on the cross of Calvary'*. Where the Roman officials threw a dice on his cloth for a cause, reason or to find out the next person to investigate the issue at hand – as a scenario and possibility for dying on the cross of calvary. According to the first four books of the New Testament *'Then the soldiers nailed him to the cross. They divided his clothes and threw dice* to decide who would get each piece'*. These are mysteries and secrets associated with the Biblical books and life which justifies the various schools of thoughts and philosophical world of intelligence. This is a clear justification for the creation of the **School of Lotteries and Bettings** and its impacts on world development. The betting industry as a school is dealing with contents such as Fractional odds, algorithms, programming languages etc as indicated above . These are schools of thoughts worth teaching and learning which gives a justification for its representation in the university. Every concept or argument is subject to a lot of assessment, validation and correction before acceptance by all. It is not everything that is consumable can be eaten by all as has been read in the biblical books. Where God asked peter to kill it and eat since everything is cleansed and acceptable

unto God. But even that, everything is subject to our own will even though God recommends allowing His will to be done in our lives as can be seen in the books of Moses.

3.5 Mineral gold production coupled with Human Gold Production and Theological Exploration besides Political applications

3.5.1 Mineral Gold Production

Gold as a precious mineral is very expensive when it comes to exploration, discovery, mining and refining to obtain a pure quality mineral for exploits. For exploits is looking at where it can be sold for millions of pounds (M£) towards enrichment of oneself or towards greatness attainment in life. In terms of the enrichment in life is where the gold is quantified in monetary terms after selling and obtained money is used to buy or build mansions, buy cars, establish big companies, help the needy or poor in society, meet the SDG's, help build a better country or world. It is also used as ornaments for decoration and beauty especially in the case of ancient chiefs and rich men and women. It is been used in this direction but on a lower level due to its huge price tag in this 21st century, difficulty in accessing the mineral and the needed input or effort against cost of investments. It is easy to access with machines but can the common illegal gold miner afford the price or buy one earth moving machine for illegal gold mining in Ghana?

Mineral gold production is accessed through rock mining, surface mining, or on water bodies. Rock mining is where pure gold is accessed from rocks by crushing rocks and embarking on due processing for the real gold in high purity of Karat. This gold is either accessed legally through standard operating procedures like at Newmont Akyem, Newmont Ahafo, Anglogold Ashanti, Persues Mines, Tarkwa Mines, Bogoso Mines etc. But a big question to ask is Anglogold comparable to Anlo – gold? (Volta land 'Anlo' – gold or? This is a big question worth analyzing from the perspective of tribalism, politics and creation intelligence. It's a research question worth further investigating and probing. The above listed gold mining companies are all involved in legal gold mining business and operations generating several gold bars per week, per month and yearly towards town development, region development, country and world development. All development are towards enrichment and greatness attainment but in different dimensions. A good example is in meeting the Sustainable Development Goals (SGD's) of the United Nations and embarking on World Bank projects for the goodwill of all citizens and people worldwide. This same gold is also accessed illegally in Ghana and Nsutam is no exception. The illegal gold mining business in Ghana always comes with a repercussion. The consequences here is the destroying of land resources, water resources, forest reserves, destruction of animals and aquatic habitats and finally the loss of human lives. This is seen on a lighter note on the part of the International gold mining companies due to standardization and the use of standard operating procedures (SOP's). This is what entails in mineral gold

production. That is gold obtained from rocks, soil and in water bodies and refined to a high purity state for enrichment, greatness attainment and meeting SDG's worldwide by the UN.

But one shouldn't just be interested in the precious mineral but the difficult and troubling journey towards attainment and final purity in karate or state. Anything worth much in life is worth suffering and acquiring and this is great philosophy associated with gold production worldwide. And this is the case for the mineral gold production worldwide by all legal gold mining companies or from the illegal gold miner (Galamseyers).

3.5.2 Human Gold Production

Gold status attainment and analysis highly depends on view point in life. Everyone and his/her perception, view point in life and understanding level based on the school of thought under consideration. Everything in life or reality boils down to how one sees or perceives it. There is what is called human gold production in life which is another school of thought. This is in two folds; human gold production through the education system and biblical grounds human gold production. The biblical human gold production basically deals with once faith and believe and ability to anchor and struggle through that faith towards greatness or richness attainment in society or country. This will be expatiated in the next sub topic. The human gold production through the education system or educating oneself in school structures or buildings is also explained here.

3.5.2.1 Human gold production through the education system

The human gold production through the education system according to Danquah and Amposah (2024), is explained in this way. The human gold production looks at how one identifies academia or learning in school structures/buildings as the ultimate path and root towards greatness or enrichment in life (refined real gold status). And hence justifies it by climbing the academic ladder from kindergarten to doctor of philosophy (PHD) level and beyond. The basic concept here is seeing a cell as the basic unit of life. Again viewing that, the basic unit of a building or house is a block or brick. The justification here is sowing a seed into the soil in good faith and allowing it to germinate under favorable or unfavorable conditions. Then nurturing it through weeding, mulching, irrigation, pruning, fertilization etc into a giant tree that feeds all with thousand birds playing and laying in it unto the next generation. In this case, one goes through a series or all kinds of learning (about 85% books usage), courses and programs after a well-defined choice of program, profession, career or a school of thought. The student or individual goes through all the pressures, the hustles, struggles, money issues (*sika asem*) associated with education and mid night burning of candles for several years. This is what one goes through and in doing so, builds a very strong foundation and faith in a chosen field or path through academia with associated spirituality level. All in the name of being refined into pure gold medal, bar or refined individual or personality for greater works or to

impact generations in the future. This is where real gold products in the form of graduates are obtained in various fields to help build the nation and world. This research work is justified in doing same for now and future generations through well-defined school building structures that meets the demands of this technological age. With this engineers, lawyers, agriculturists, scientists, artist, business men and women, footballers and other professionals will be trained, refined and obtained as pure gold bars products to serve mankind and future generations. The pure gold products has the potential of serving town, region, and nation or being boxed and shipped to other countries to help build a beautiful world for all. We or most people are finding themselves on the international stage to help build a country or impact the world through this process. Since there are different schools of thoughts and motive for actions and inactions. For instance, another school of thought can be thinking of working on the human penis as a gold production business. These are all schools of thoughts and philosophical intelligent world of creation motives identified through investigations and research. Where one thinks to be seen as man or real man is highly dependent on manhood largeness and size. Where another world of creation thinks real man is highly dependent on intelligence or knowledge level and to another is the quantum of money in the pocket and wealth. These are all human gold production intelligent creations and schools of thoughts.

With a justification for mineral gold production as explained above which balances human gold production, refined man is able to explore, engineer and mine real gold as a refined gold product on planet earth. And then initiate the use of real mineral gold to address needs such as SDG's of the United Nations (UN) and for World Bank projects. The gold is used as real gold or quantified in terms of monetary languages usable by all. This helps to address all the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG's) as there will be eradication of poverty, hunger, promote good health and well-being, give quality education (quality human gold production), address gender equality, provide water and electricity for all. From the sustainable development goals (SDG's) is also peace and justice establishment among citizens and finally, ensures partnership, collaboration and coordination among all the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG's) for the United Nations and embark on World Bank projects for the good will of all mankind worldwide.

3.5.2.2 Human Gold Production and theological foundations from the Christian perspective

The Bible is made up of books which contains inspirational words from the highest being (God) and meant for correction, nurturing, training and pruning mankind into a refined gold products acceptable unto God himself. This refined human gold products becomes tools or instruments to be used for glorification and accomplishing tasks and missions in His vineyard. This biblical books talks or deals in human gold production but not directly written in the scriptures. But from the concept of schools of thought is a justification for this. The whole

concept of the great commission task by Jesus in the Bible is the foundation or basis for human gold production in the Bible. 'Jesus came and told his disciples, I have been given all authority in heaven and on earth. Therefore go and make disciples of all the nations, baptizing them in the name of the Father and the son and the Holy Spirit. Teach these new disciples to obey all the commands I have given you. And be sure of this; I am with you always, even to the end of the age'. This is the '**Great Commission**' task from Jesus to his disciples (**11 disciples comparable to 11 players forming a football team?**) before ascension into the heavens after his salvation work on planet earth. This forms the foundational message and basis for the Christian gospel and family. After the acceptance of Christ into once life and being baptized into the Christian family is the process for work input for once own salvation with fear and trembling at any point in time throughout the Christian journey on earth. This comes with reading the Bible, prayers, fasting, meditations, fellowship and all kinds of religious sacrifices, rituals and activities. All these rituals are geared toward obtaining a good Christian in the vineyard of God and for the work of God. This is also coupled with teachings, correction, counselling's, help and support from Christians or believers who are at the level of chewing bones as such a person will still be breastfeeding in the vineyard of God. This is seeing life as a dependent and independent figure towards a refined human gold product. The implication here is the mature Christian offering help and support to the new or young believer or babe Christian. Such a young believer or Christian is subject to all kinds of trails, tribulations, fights, hunger, torcher, anguish and all kinds of unnecessary conditions and wilderness from the accuser or enemy. And such a Christian should be willing to pass the examination here through personal hardwork and fight with some support from the mature Christian. The final justification after going through the trials, anguish, torcher and standing tall and strong in the Christian faith to pass the examination is a refined human gold product. That will be formed and fashioned for good use in the vineyard of God towards good works and glorification. This is comparable to refinement of mineral gold by passing it through fire and obtaining refined real gold with high purity and karat. This is summarized in the book of 1 Peter as '*So be truly glad, there is a wonderful joy ahead even though you have to endure many trials for a little while. The trials will show that your faith is genuine. It is being tested as fire test and purifies gold – though your faith is far more precious than mere gold. So when your faith remains strong through many trials, it will bring you much praise and glory and honour on the day when Jesus Christ is revealed to the whole world*'. These are the words of Apostle Peter to the church or Christian's family concerning trails, tribulation, pain, anguish etc which are legal or illegal gold mining associated issues. These issues are repercussions one does goes through in real life, in the Christian faith or as a gold mining engineer to obtain real mineral gold legally or illegally (Galamsey). This is what the whole church doctrine, concept and process is about. In summary is shown below;

- It all begins with the identification of a need, problem, sin factor and hence a salvation hand or man
- After this is the confession for sins and inactions;
- Then accepting Jesus Christ as Lord and personal savior;
- Baptism with flowing water (comparable to Jesus baptism in River Jordan) – Cleansing of oneself with water from dirt as detailed in Danquah (2026) paper.
- Then baptism of the Holy Ghost; That is baptism of the Spirit to commune and communicate with God and that is Baptism of the spirit by the Holy Ghost;
- Working out of once own salvation with fear and trembling coupled with additions, subtractions, protections, counselling's and monitoring from mature believers in the Christendom or Christian family; The whole concept of faith, trials, tribulations and gold refinement and processing stages in the human gold production business is seen here;
- At the maturity level in the Christian journey will be the final refined human gold products for greater works in God's vineyard and world development to propagate the gospel unto future generations.

This final refined human gold product is the treasure to propagate the gospel to the ends of the world. Such a human gold product is the new leader to lead the next generation through the same church gold mining or religious gold mining process. These refined human gold products are embedded with spiritual gifts and justified as Apostles, Prophets, Pastors, Teachers, Miracle workers, etc for the edification of the church. The basic spiritual gift unto all is a teacher as everyone on earth is seen teaching in various ways. So everyone has a spiritual gift as can be seen in the book of 1 Corinthians. This is comparable to a lecturer, engineer, Dentist or Doctor who is now a human gold product from another school of thought to help build a better world and leave it in the hands of the next generation. This will be towards meeting the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UN SDG's) and Working out World Bank projects to help the most vulnerable in society. This most vulnerable person is comparable to a sinner who doesn't know God and needs to accept Christ as Lord and personal saviour and taking through the human gold production process like a clay in potter's hand. This clay is worked on and taking through several processes towards obtaining a final product with defined quality and beauty for glorification and enrichment in life. This is the human gold production in the direction of the Christian faith and is possibly same in other religious bodies or doctrines like the Moslem, the Buddhist, Traditionalist or idol worshipper etc. A good example explaining this three gold mining concepts and philosophy elaborated above are Newmont Akyem at Abirim (Now Zijin Golden Ridge Limited), the University of

Environment and Sustainable Development (UESD) under construction at Bunso and the Church of Pentecost in Eastern Region salvation work. The current state of water resources in the Eastern Region is very bad as all water bodies have been destroyed due to illegal gold mining activities and business in the region. These water bodies are a function and foundation stones when it comes to Christian faith, usage and importance in the human gold production in the direction of the Christian perspective and theological backgrounds. This can be seen in another paper as written by Danquah (2026). These water resources need to be worked on for a balance between water on land, water above and water underground in order to protect and conserve the hydrological cycle. A whole school of thought worth probing further in this 2025/2026 under the NDC government.

The Newmont Akyem gold mining project is a project modelled from Newmont Ahafo gold mining project and the current status in terms of legal gold mining business, operation and management in Ghana and worldwide. With this intelligence, model and further work is the current number of gold mining companies like Transeco, BSD, CG Mining, Narawa etc which are to be worked on and elevated to Newmont Akyem at Abirim (now Zijin Golden Ridge Limited) status with pulling and building intelligence (principal/capital or resources). This has raised a lot of interests and concerns after work done and high interest in gold mining business and its operations in the Eastern Region of Ghana. These are worth investigating further with the region as resources are to be protected, managed and kept for now and future generations.

3.5.3 Gold mining business creation coupled with Tribal and Political competition in this 21st Century

Ghana in this 21st Century is seeing a creation around this gold mining intelligence and creation and the major question being asked by all (from all schools of thoughts); which tribe or country is ascribed to this gold mining business in Ghana and worldwide? Or which country worldwide is responsible for this gold mining project or initiating the gold mining business creation intelligence that was done years back and shot into the world to pilot or spearhead the world to today. A justification of gold mining business creation towards a day for another creation to take the next generation or world to another level? Is it the Akwapim man, is it the Ashanti Man, is it the northerner, is it the Fante man, is it the Ewe man, is it the Ga man, is it the Akyem man, is it the Kwahu man, is it the Kyerepong man or is it any other tribe in Ghana. Or is it the British, is it the India man, is it the American man, is the Portuguese, is it the French man, is it the German, is it the man from Burkina Faso or is it any man from another country. Is it from the New Patriotic Party (NPP), is it from the National Democratic Congress (NDC), and is it from the Democrats or from the Republican, or from which political party worldwide?

From research and investigations, the current legal and illegal gold mining activities and impacts in Ghana is a scenario from past creation, activities, actions and inactions when

talking about gold mining business on planet earth. Therefore, who is responsible for this creation based on tribal, country or political grounds? And assuming this creation was done 200 years ago and shot to take off or spearhead the world to the next level, to the next generation; where are the creators, implementers and all those who did this hard work? Aren't they dead and gone with the planet earth or world in place for new creations, inventions, modifications, additions and subtractions for the good will of all? Where is their wealth, riches, greatness, intelligence and contributions to humanity and world development? It is only records in books or internet that can record or talk about such great men dreams, works, dreams and contributions to world creation and development in life. This is what justifies dreams and greatness embedded in books, in the grave and spiritual realms. This is the reason for the Christian faith which believes in spiritual realm operation coupled with physical realm manifestation before God and all mankind for the advancement of the world unto the next generations.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The 21st Century mineral gold and human gold mining business is seeing battling from all angles for justification and validation of ownership and greatness height in world governance and rulership. But if everything is towards the goodwill of humanity and mankind, then the United Nations (one united world composed of different countries with its citizens and having all mankind at will and at heart) Sustainable Development Goals should be the main objective for all towards equitable sharing of resources. The equitable sharing of country or world resources is highly dependent on ability, intelligence level, education level, experience and impact towards country development, world development and greatness. That is the minister of the Gospel and minister in Parliament or governance, the engineer, the scientist, the artist, the security personnel and all schools of thoughts graduates will contribute their parts towards mineral gold and human gold production for the goodwill of all mankind worldwide. The need and importance to know that everyone is important when it talking about impact, effect and world development. And hence a justification for someone to hold just a single match stick at a corner on planet earth towards world development, growth and propagation of the gold mining business worldwide. This will help meet the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG's) for the good will and wellbeing of mankind while embarking on World Bank projects in order to meet the financial needs of all.

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References

- Danquah, I. O., Amposah, G, 2024, Geotechnical Investigation and Assessment of Modern Building Foundation, Journal for Studies in Management and Planning, India.